

DETECTION OF CASES OF INTERNATIONAL OFFENSES AND CRIME IN INTERNATIONAL LAW AND TO ELIMINATE THEM

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An international offense is an act or omission of a subject of international law, as a result of which the subject violates the norms of international law and its international obligations, causing material or intangible damage to other subjects of international law or the international community as a whole. In this case, the liability arises from international law as a result of the damage caused by the subjects. Thus, the components of an international offense that give rise to international legal liability are:

- Actions and inactions of the subject in violation of international law;
- the ability of a subject of international law to commit an offense;
- harm of another subject of international law and a group of subjects by a subject of international law.

ABSTRACT

Today, the formation and development of international criminal law is a mandatory and necessary measure taken as a result of the growing number of international offenses, and cooperation between states in this area is constantly improving on a legal basis. The number of such offenses are growing. In them, the main object of criminal aggression is international law, which regulates relations in the field of crime and the fight against crime. Therefore, when we talk about offenses on the scale of international law, we can speak of minor offenses as well as international crimes. In this article, we will focus on the concepts of international law, international offenses, and international responsibility.

It is also not allowed to be ignorant of the norms of international law or to misinterpret or misinterpret it. Almost all offenses are committed consciously, on the basis of a well-thought-out plan, and through guilt. It is well known that there is no need to overstate the fact that millions of innocent people are suffering as a result of slavery, mercenary crime, terrorism, hostage-taking and other crimes that are recognized as international crimes today.

International experts estimate that the annual revenue from human trafficking worldwide exceeds \$ 7 billion (US). According to the UN, there are about 2 million people in the world every year. 700,000 people are victims of human trafficking. It is also necessary to emphasize terrorism and terrorist acts. Because millions of people are dying as a result. Therefore, it is important to develop appropriate measures to

prevent international crimes. The fight against international crime requires the creation of a legal framework for international cooperation and the development of forms of legal cooperation. If we consider that the legal basis of international cooperation in the fight against crime is part of international criminal law, then the issues of international cooperation in the fight against crime, defined in international legal instruments, can be divided into the following system of principles and norms:

- a) The recognition by States of the serious danger of particular criminal acts to the whole international community and the need for joint measures to prevent them;
- b) coordinating measures to prevent crimes of an international nature;
- c) the jurisdiction of States over crimes of an international character and the imposition of penalties for crimes committed;
- d) the conduct of special investigations, the search for offenders and the provision of mutual legal assistance in criminal matters;
- e) to study the problems of international crime and to take measures against them;
- f) exchange of information on the fight against crime.

It is known that international law studies the problems related to the international management of political, economic, cultural, military and other relations between states, ie interstate relations, which arise in the process of their cooperation. R.A. Kalamakryan and R.A. According to Muellerson, international offense is a network designed to protect subjects of international law from criminal encroachment on the international legal order and includes the principles and norms of states' liability for crimes of an international and international nature, as well as criminal prosecution of guilty individuals. A.X. According to Saidov, international crime is

the violation of the obligations of states to ensure the vital interests of the international community as an act of international law. Cooperation in the fight against crime is carried out on the basis of multilateral and bilateral agreements, as well as in the framework of universal and regional organizations. International criminal law is a complex independent branch of modern international law. The norms of international criminal law will focus on two subjects, namely the cooperation of states on mutual powers and obligations, and the criminal liability of individuals for international crimes.

The norms of the national legislation of different countries on the same issue play a special role in the emergence of the usual norms of international criminal law. For example, criminal laws to combat international terrorism and mercenaries may help to establish a customary norm of international law on the liability of perpetrators before individual international judicial bodies. The same laws are actively used in the development and adoption of international agreements on combating drug trafficking and drug trafficking in general. But it is unreasonable to consider national legislation as a source of international criminal law. The list of sources of international law is complete and generally recognized. Article 38 of the Statute (Charter) of the UN International Court of Justice influences the development of international law by affirming or noting that court decisions, precedents, which are included in ancillary sources of international law, do not have this or that international legal norm. The example of the verdict of the Nuremberg military tribunal showed the impact of the above court decision on the formation of the principles and clear norms of international criminal law. As a result of the decision of the

UN General Assembly, the world community views these principles as based on universally recognized, previously formed norms of international law. The Nuremberg Principles will be the legal basis for the adoption of international legal instruments on liability for genocide, apartheid, ecocide and other international crimes. Unlike domestic criminal law, in international criminal law, not only individuals but also states and, in some cases, legal entities can be held liable as subjects of crimes. In this case, the state can be held liable only in the case of an international crime. A universal convention on the responsibility of states is currently being prepared. In this case, the state can be held liable only in the case of an international crime. A universal convention on the responsibility of states is currently being prepared. Article 5 of the draft Code of Crimes Against Peace and Human Security, adopted at the 46th session of the International Law Commission in 1994, states: or failure to take action does not absolve from responsibility. "It should be noted that this article is not about the international criminal liability of the state, but about the responsibility of states under international law. It is therefore unlikely that it would be legally correct to call a state a subject of international crime. In fact, the state is the subject of responsibility for international crimes. And again, states are held politically and materially liable for international crimes, and criminal law sanctions do not apply to them. Various non-governmental organizations, including the International Criminal Law Association and the International Society for Social Protection, are making significant contributions to the fight against crime, including in the fight against international crime. They develop conventions on international criminal law and international

criminal justice and prepare the texts of international conventions, then provide advice to the UN and its agencies, help to unite experts and forces of different countries in the fight against crime. The International Criminal Law Association (ICAA) is an international non-governmental organization whose mission is to improve the legal institutions and criminal procedure and penitentiary legislation to ensure the efficiency and humanity of justice, and to prepare its activities for international congresses (every five years), and leads in the form of a transfer. It also develops recommendations for the UN. The congresses of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) deal with the arrest of criminals, drug trafficking, environmental protection under criminal law, international terrorism and other issues. The only interagency international organization directly involved in the fight against international crime is the International Criminal Police Organization. It is no exaggeration to say that the International Criminal Police Organization coordinates the activities of criminal police services of different countries in the search and arrest of criminals.

In conclusion, international cooperation in the field of combating international crime is one of the main areas of international law, which is part of international criminal law and serves to ensure international law and domestic law and order, as well as international and national security. Due to the versatility of these forms of international cooperation, they are implemented in two main forms: first, within international bodies and organizations, ie at the international institutional level, and secondly, on the basis of international agreements, in international law.

It should be noted that given the emergence of new forms of international

crime, but the lack of methods and tools to prevent it, and most important thing is that, the mechanism of interstate international cooperation, international law provides for

international cooperation in the fight against crime, a special convention must be developed as a document.

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